

THE INFLUENCE OF CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS ON SPEECH CULTURE

*N. Petrosyan*¹

Abstract:

This article is dedicated to a problem of critical thinking and speech culture. Communicative competence is considered one of the main categories of speech culture, so it is important to know the basic communicative qualities of speech, such as accuracy, consistency, richness, diversity of speech, purity and expressiveness. Critical thinking abilities are closely related to speech components, namely normative, communicative and ethical.

Key words: culture, speech, critical, thinking, professional suitability, knowledge, the norms of the literary language, communication.

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Globalization and the development of the world community have dramatically increased the need for learning foreign languages. Modern pedagogy needs to rethink the changes in the educational space that took place in previous years and continue nowadays. Society, as a whole, needs qualitatively new characteristics of pedagogical activities. Currently, the introduction of innovative, progressive pedagogical technologies in the educational process, the constant improvement of the professional skills of teachers, the improvement of their preparation for the implementation of the educational process at a high theoretical and methodological level, the ability to use advanced teaching methods is becoming relevant.

Along with the research conducted in the world on the use of pedagogical technologies in teaching foreign languages, special attention is paid to the improvement of existing techniques and the creation of new methods of teaching oral and written speech, in this case, the use of modern technologies for the development of critical thinking, based on the authentic materials which develops speech culture. In this regard, it becomes obvious that the formation of students' communicative competence largely depends on the use of innovative pedagogical technologies, which in turn increases the effectiveness of the lesson and the quality of students' knowledge.

Language teachers usually employ innovative pedagogical methods without addressing the particular needs, set of habits, cultural background as well as areas of weakness of students they teach. Much has been done to develop the teaching strategies in terms of language learning.

Nunan argues: "The teachers need to be aware that motivation is a consideration in determining whether or not learners are willing to communicate. Clearly, the more

¹ *Petrosyan Nelya Valerevna, PhD, docent of the chair of «The English language history and grammar», Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages*

meaningful the materials and the tasks are for the learners involved the better the outcome will be" [S. Krashen, 2008, p.27-35].

Ur develops this idea by suggesting that good language classes are ones where learners do a great deal of self-study work using different language skills, participation and motivation are high and the used language is at an acceptable level. The flaws in English language teaching are responsible for inadequate performance on the part of second language learners, since the teaching methodology focuses mainly on the reading and writing skills leading to the encouragement of spoken competence. The culture of speech is the ability to express your thoughts clearly and clearly, to speak competently, the ability not only to attract attention with your speech, but also to influence listeners, the possession of the culture of speech is a kind of characteristic of professional suitability for people of various professions: diplomats, lawyers, politicians, teachers of schools and universities, radio and television workers, managers, journalists.

The culture of speech is understood as: 1) knowledge of the norms of the literary language in its oral and written forms; 2) the ability to choose and organize language means that, in a certain communication situation, contribute to the achievement of communication objectives; 3) compliance with the ethics of communication [Л.А.Введенская, 2003, с.25].

Thus, the culture of speech contains three components: normative, communicative and ethical. The culture of speech presupposes, first of all, the correctness of speech, that is, compliance with the norms of the literary language, which are perceived by its native speakers as an "ideal", a model. The language norm is the central concept of language culture, and the normative aspect of speech culture is considered one of the most important.

However, the culture of speech cannot be reduced to a list of prohibitions and definitions of "right-wrong". The concept of "speech culture" is associated with the laws and peculiarities of language functioning, as well as with speech activity in all its diversity. It also includes the opportunity provided by the language system to find an adequate language form for expressing specific content in each real situation of speech communication.

The culture of speech develops skills of selection and use of language means in the process of speech communication, helps to form a conscious attitude to their use in speech practice in accordance with communicative tasks. The choice of language means is necessary for this purpose as it is the basis of speech culture.

Communicative expediency is considered one of the main categories of the theory of speech culture, therefore it is important to know the basic communicative qualities of speech that have the best impact on the addressee, taking into account the specific situation and in accordance with the goals and objectives. These include: accuracy, consistency, richness and diversity of speech, its purity, expressiveness.

The ethical aspect of speech culture prescribes the knowledge and application of the rules of linguistic behavior in specific situations. Under the ethical standards of communication refers to speech etiquette (speech formulas greetings, requests, questions, thanks, greetings, etc.; to appeal to "you" and "you"; the choice of a full or abbreviated name, formula, treatment, etc.).

The use of speech etiquette is greatly influenced by extra-linguistic factors: the age of participants of the speech act (the purposeful actions of speech), their social

status, the nature of the relationship between them (formal, informal, friendly, intimate), the time and place of communication, etc.

The ethical component of the culture of speech imposes a strict ban on profanity in the process of communication, condemns the conversation in "raised tones". The culture of communication is inherently connected with the formation and development of critical thinking skills, since critical thinking is a mental means of human activity.

Critical thinking is a widely used term that includes the skills of identifying, analyzing, synthesizing and evaluating information for making informed decisions [D.F. Halpern, 2001, p. 273].

The most adequate interpretation of the term critical thinking is presented by E.I. Fedotovskaya. According to the researcher, critical thinking is inherently connected with the reflection of students' activities, and includes the following characteristics of thinking [Е.И. Федотовская, 2005, p.180]:

analytical thinking (analysis of information, selection of necessary facts, comparison and comparison of facts or events);

associative thinking (establishing associations with previously acquired material, familiar facts, events; establishing associations with new features of the subject),

logical thinking (the ability to logically justify proposed solutions to a specific problem and follow a logical sequence of actions when presenting solutions),

systems of thinking (the ability to analyze the object of learning, the problem and its characteristics).

For example, «Concept mapping» is a diagram used to visually organize information. The mental map is hierarchical and shows the relationships between the parts of the whole. It is often created around a single concept, drawn as an image in the center of a blank page, to which are added related representations of ideas, such as images, words, and parts of words. The main ideas are directly related to the central concept, and other ideas branch off from these main ideas.

Mental maps can also be drawn manually, for example, as "notes" during a lecture, meeting, or planning session, or as higher-quality images when more time is available. Mental maps are considered a kind of spider diagrams.

Tony Buzan - British psychologist, author of the method of memorization, creativity and organization of thinking "mind maps". The author and co-author of more than 100 books. Mind Maps was created by Tony Buzan in 1970. It was first presented to the world in the spring of 1974 after the publication of the book "Work with your Head". We all loved picture books as children, and many still do. And this is correct, because it is useful for the development of intelligence, according to psychologists [M.Lloyd, 2010, p.5-16].

Buzan's specific approach and introduction of the term "mental map" originated during a 1974 BBC television series he hosted called Use Your Head. In this show and the accompanying book series, Buzan promoted his concept of a radial tree by schematizing keywords in a colorful, shining, tree-like structure.

Buzan says that this idea was inspired by the general semantics of Alfred Korzybski, popularized in science fiction novels such as those of Robert A. Heinlein and A. E. Van Vogt. He argues that while "traditional" outlines force readers to scan

from left to right and top to bottom, readers actually tend to scan the entire page in a non-linear way. The Buzan technique also uses popular assumptions about the functions of the brain's hemispheres to explain the claimed increased effectiveness of mental mapping compared to other forms of note-taking (Buzan, 2012).

Mental maps serve a different purpose: they help with memory and organization. Mental maps are sets of words structured by the author's mental context using visual mnemonics, and, through the use of color, icons, and visual connections, are informal and necessary for the proper functioning of the mental map.

An intelligence map is a method of processing and memorizing information, creative tasks, and a tool for developing memory and thinking. The intellectual map has the following properties: visibility; attractiveness; memorability; creative approach; possibility of revision. The logical framework for measuring critical thinking skills has defined critical thinking as a process consisting of three main parts. The first part is a problem-solving process in the context of interaction with the world and people in general. The second part is a process of reasoning based on basic knowledge and previously specified facts, conclusions drawn by induction, deduction and value judgment. The last part reveals the decision based on the understanding of the necessary information.

However, despite the different levels of critical thinking, university students should be able to identify problems in order to rationally synthesize and solve them. To solve the problems, recipients must fend off various hypotheses and offer appropriate conclusions based on indirect information, in the absence of the necessary knowledge or evidence. A hypothesis can be proven to be true if it is actually supported by the facts given, which is a much more objective proof of the true conclusion.

Summarizing the above, we can conclude that critical thinking is defined as the ability and willingness of individuals to reflect on their own and others' thinking in relation to its truth, value and validity in a logical argument. The culture of speech, communicative expediency, ethical norms also depend on the ability to critically comprehend information. The communicative qualities of speech are formed through the construction of critical thinking skills, which inherently affects the ethical norms of communication.

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